

THE EFFECT OF COORDINATION AND LEADERSHIP CAPABILITIES ON CORPORATE HOTEL FACILITIES' PERFORMANCE IN KENYA

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Abstract

Coordination and leadership play a critical role in performance management and set the space for performance by providing feedback coaching, guidance and fostering a teamwork culture of excellence. The role of coordination capabilities in enhancing the performance of business organizations is well documented in strategic management literature. This study explores the influence of coordination and leadership capabilities and how their deployment affects hotel facilities' performance in Kenya. The study employed a cross-sectional research design in which one hundred and fifty (150) managers of different hospitality facilities in Kenya were surveyed using a questionnaire, and the data were statistically analyzed. The relationship between coordination, leadership capabilities deployment, and hotel performance has had few empirical studies done. The gap in knowledge has been exacerbated by multiple definitions, ambiguity of constructs, contradicting views and little grounding of the theory in empirical observation. The two constructs are dynamic capabilities and affect the host of other aspects that affect performance effectiveness. The research focused on investigating whether coordination and leadership capabilities intrinsic presence in organizations translates to organizational performance in hotels and how coordination and leadership deployment influence performance. The study borrowed from the dynamic-capabilities theory that is grounded in the resource-based view (RBV), which assumes that firms require certain capabilities to be successful and responsive to the (dynamic) changes in their environment by creating, integrating, and modifying their resource base (Teece, 2007; Beske, 2012; Helfat et al., 2007). Like for example, a technological disruption, or post Covid19 hospitality facilities have had to adapt their portfolio of resources. The objective is to assess the effect of deployment of coordinated leadership on hotel performance. The expected result will indicate the influence of coordination and leadership capability deployment and how they impact performance by building valuable insight in assisting hospitality facilities' organizational effectiveness.

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1. INTRODUCTION

An organization's ability to sustain itself over time is related to its performance (Hofer and Schedel, 1978). It is usually seen as a measure of how efficiently and effectively managers use available resources to satisfy customers and achieve set goals. Two words are important in this matter, Efficiency and Effectiveness; efficiency is seen as a measure of how well or how productively resources are used to achieve a goal, while effectiveness is a measure of the appropriateness of the goals that the organization is seeking and the level of achievement. According to Ibraimi (2014), the relationship between strategy and performance can contribute to greater effectiveness for individual firms and entire economies, and thus hotels whose performance influences the national economy and the entire hospitality and tourism industry.

The service industry is highly heterogeneous, encompassing complex and innovative activities, and it continues to grow compared with tangible goods. According to the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), the service industry comprises approximately 70% of aggregate production and employment in these nations (OECD, 2012). The hotel industry is a key service sector. A review of past studies revealed a multidimensional conceptualization of organizational performance related predominantly to stakeholders, heterogeneous product market circumstances, and time. A review of the operationalization of performance highlights the limited effectiveness of commonly accepted measurement practices in tapping multidimensionality. The primary focus of strategic management as a body of knowledge is how organizations generate and sustain advantages (Abrosini and Bowwan, 2000). Most strategic management studies have measured performance using conventional measures of economic prosperity based on shareholder approaches. The two most popular measures related to the economic prosperity of performance are return on assets and sales growth.

1.1 Coordination

Coordination is a management function that ensures that different departments and groups work in harmony to achieve the set goals. Through coordination the unity of action among employees, groups, and departments is achieved. It synchronizes the conduct of different tasks and activities to achieve set objectives efficiently. According to Saunders, Skinner, Dietz, Gillespie, & Lewicki (2010), organizations and their composites are increasingly being tied to managing unfamiliar relationships with unfamiliar parties and competitors. These relationships involve not only working across various national cultures, but also various professional cultures and even different areas of internal specialization. The features of coordination are the integration, unification and synchronization of the efforts of the departments and groups to provide unity of action for pursuing common goals. Since functions change according to the stage of work, management can always make special efforts to improve operations for effectiveness.

1.1.2 Coordination and Leadership in Hospitality Industry management

A manager in a hotel could hold a senior position within a hospitality business, either as a general manager within hotel business as a senior manager for a tourism or hospitality business, or working in revenue management. As a leader in hospitality he is responsible for inspiring their teams, moving them toward common goals and emphasizing exceptional customer service. The kitchen, front office operations, room division, management, finance, and marketing teams must be able to coordinate effectively with each other. Team leaders must be able to delegate and coordinate many tasks simultaneously and communicate with managers from other divisions. However, coordination is not leadership; leadership is much more. Leadership involves taking everything that one knows and setting direction. Hospitality operations are different from many other organizations in terms of

how one achieves a leadership role and how its scope is determined. However, the fundamental need for a person or group to make decisions, articulate a direction, and lead forward motion remains.

1.1.3 Coordination Capability Deployment Process

Coordination/integration capability describes a firm's ability to assess the value of existing resources and integrate them to shape new competences (Teece, 2011; Allred et al., 2011). Moreover, the implementation of new configurations of functional competences lies in the effective coordination of a variety of tasks and resources and the synchronization of different activities (Frese, 2008; Helfat et al., 2007). Coordination incorporates governance, which is defined as the way and practice of directing, organizing, and controlling an organization. Coordination processes connect and interface single routines through communication, scheduling, task assignment, and other related activities. (Teece, 2007). The lack of efficient coordinating and combining of different resources and tasks may explain why apparently slight technological changes have overwhelming effects on incumbent firms' competitive positions in a market. Learning capability can be conceived of as a principal means of strategic renewal. Renewal requires organizations to explore and learn new ways while at the same time exploit what they have already learned. (Teece, 2010) argue that learning is a very important process that, through experimentation and repetition, leads to better and quicker resolution of specific problems and, at the same time, enables firms to identify new production opportunities.

1.2 Leadership

Researchers have defined leadership in accordance with their individual perspectives and the aspects of the phenomenon of most interest to them. After a review of the leadership literature, Silver, and Alberto (2016) concluded that leadership consists of many variables. Stogdill (1974, p259) concluded that there are almost as many definitions of leadership as there are persons who have attempted to define the concept. The stream of new definitions has continued unabated since Stogdill's observation in the study of Winston, Bruce E, and Kathreen Patterson (2006). It is defined in terms of traits, behaviors, influences, interaction patterns, role relationships, and occupation of a position. Leadership is an interaction between persons in which one presents information of a sort and in such a manner that the other is convinced that his outcomes will be improved if he behaves in the manner suggested or desired" (Jacobs, 1970, p. 232). Leadership is the initiation and maintenance of structure in expectation and interaction (Stogdill, 1974, p. 411). According to Terry (1977), leadership is the relationship in which one person, the leader, influences others to work together willingly on related tasks to attain that which the leader desires. It is the influential increment over and above mechanical compliance with the routine directives of the organization" (Katz & Kahn, 1978, p. 528). According to Bray, Campbell and Grant, leadership is the effectiveness in getting ideas accepted and in guiding a group or an individual to accomplish a task (Morris, 1979, p. 5).

Koontz and O'Donnell define leadership as the art or process of influencing people so that they will strive willingly toward the achievement of group goals (Koontz et. al., 1984, p.661). 90. According to Bass (1985) leadership is an interaction between members of a group and leaders are agents of change whose acts affect other people more than other people's acts affect them. Interpersonal influence is exercised in a situation and directed, through the communication process, toward the attainment of a specialized goal (Hersey and Blanchard, 1982, p. 83). Leadership is the process of defining current situations and articulating goals for the future; making the decisions necessary to resolve the situation or achieve the goals; and gaining the commitment from those who have to implement these decisions (Brache, 1983, p. 120). Leadership is the process of influencing the activities of an organized group toward goal achievement" (Rauch & Behling, 1984, p. 46). Leadership involves a process in which one person exerts intentional influence over other people to guide, structure, and facilitate activities and relationships in a group or organization. This implies that one or more group members can be identified as a leader according to some observable difference between the person(s) and other members, who are referred to as

followers or subordinates. According to Janda (1960), the definition of leadership as a phenomenon involves the interaction between two or more persons. In addition, most definitions of leadership reflect the assumption that leadership involves an influencing process in which intentional influence is exerted by the leader over followers. The various definitions of leadership explicit little else in common. They differ in many respects, including important differences regarding who exerts influence, the purpose of the attempts to influence, and the manner in which influence is exerted.

2. Performance in Hotels

Performance in organizations can be assessed at three levels, first at the functional level where the focus is individual performance in aggregate units. Second, at the business level, the focus is on SBUs and at the corporate level, the focus is on the outcome of an entire group of related SBUs under central corporate leadership (Pearce & Robinson, 2007). This study assesses performance at the corporate level, mostly employing non-financial indicators.

The balanced score card (BSC) is a management system that maps an organization's strategic objectives into performance metrics from four perspectives: financial, internal process, customers, learning, and growth. BSC emphasizes a comprehensive and holistic approach to performance evaluation, and it consists of both financial and non-financial performance metrics, which are developed from financial, customer, internal business process, and learning and growth perspectives (Kaplan, 2010). Nevertheless, these measures are not stone cast. Indeed, BSC is no more than a template that can be customized for specific organizational or industry elements. The selection of perspectives should be based on what is necessary to tell the story of the strategy and create a competitive advantage for the organizations.

Indeed, hotel industry performance measurement approaches have relied more on financial results but are now being replaced by more integrated systems that combine financial and non-financial indicators (Bergin-Seers and Jago, 2007). The most important consequence of performance that is not quantified in financial terms only is the indirect yet clear linkage of performance to customer satisfaction and quality (Ghalayini and Noble, 1996). Other measures include occupancy performance, such as the average occupancy rate. Through these new approaches and their combination, performance in the hotel industry has been studied by linking performance to both external and internal factors (Pereira-Moliner et al., 2010)

1.4 Study Methodology

This study was conducted through a census survey of corporate hotel organizations in Kenya. The target population was 150 managers representing different hotel types. The questionnaires were administered to each manager, out of which 89 were returned, thus making the sample population to be 89. Questionnaires were administered to managers attending management development programs. The questionnaire was divided into 3 categories general information and variables, coordination, leadership capabilities, and performance measurement. Primary data were collected through a semi-structured questionnaire with a 5-point Likert-style scale strongly agree disagree questionnaire. The unit of analysis was corporate hotels represented by their managers in a management development program because the study was to identify the effect of coordination and leadership capabilities deployment on corporate hotels' performance in Kenya. The research was cross-sectional in that the data were gathered just once over a period of months. Analysis was performed using descriptive and inferential statistics that involved linear regression and correlation analysis that yielded coefficients for interpretation and conclusions. The following regression model was used in data analysis.

$$\text{Model 1: } Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X + \varepsilon$$

Where;

Y: Is the Hotel Performance β_0 : is a constant term for corresponding variables. X1, Coordination capability, X2 leadership capability ε : is the error term

1.4.1 Coordination capability

The respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with the statements regarding coordination. They used a Likert scale of 1-5 where 1 was strongly disagree, 2 disagree, 3 neutrals, 4 agree, and 5 strongly agree. The results of the responses were analyzed using frequencies, mean, and standard deviation. The results show that 47.8% of the respondents agreed with the statement that there is an efficient and effective

change management system in an organization, while 32% indicated that they strongly agree with the statement. The results also show that majority of the respondents (66%) agreed with the statement that the organization has developed and maintained strategic partnerships, while 22.2% indicated that they strongly agree.

The majority of respondents (60.1%) indicated that they agree with the statement that the organization continuously reviews business strategies related to operations of the market and its products, and 22.2% indicated that they strongly agree with the statement. The majority of respondents (57.1%) also agreed with the statement that there is effective coordination within the various organizational activities, resources, and services available in this organization. The results show that 27.1% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement. Overall, the findings of this study show that respondents agreed with the statements that there is an efficient and effective change management system in a hotel ($M=4.09$, $SD=.797$) and that the hotel has developed and maintained strategic partnerships ($M=4.09$, $SD=.615$). The results also show that overall, respondents agreed with the statements that the organization continuously reviews business strategies related to operations of the market and its products ($M=4.01$, $SD=.721$) and that there is effective coordination within the various organizational activities, resources, and services available in this organization ($M=4.08$, $SD=.737$). The respondents were neutral on the statements that their organization is strong in operational coordination ($M=3.23$, $SD=.620$) and that their organization collaborates with other organizations in the industry ($M=3.85$, $SD=.468$). These findings are shown in table 4.3.

Table 1.0: Descriptive Statistics Results for Coordination Capability

Statistic	N	Minimum Statistic	Maximum Statistic	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic	Skewness Statistic	Kurtosis Statistic	Std. Error	Std. Error
Our hotel is based in strong operational coordination skills	89	2	5	4.36	.70	-1.06	.26	1.41	.51
Our hotel collaborates with other industry organizations	89	3	5	4.42	.66	-.70	.26	-.53	.51
There is efficient and effective change management system in the hotel	89	5	5	3.98	.78	-.80	.26	.45	.51
The hotel has developed and maintained strategic partnerships	89	2	5	4.29	.78	-.86	.26	.17	.51
The hotel continuously reviews business strategies related to market operations and its products	89	1	5	4.36	.78	-1.04	.26	.47	.51
Effective coordination within the various hotel activities, resources, and services available	89	1	5	4.20	.86	-.97	.26	.91	.51
Leadership is involved in all coordination activities in the hotel.	89	1	5	4.38	.87	-1.47	.26	2.00	.51
Valid N (listwise)	89								

To measure coordination, respondents were asked 5 point likert scale questions where 1 was strongly disagree and 5 strongly agree. 46 % of respondents strongly agreed to the statement that their organization is strong in operational coordination, 50.6% Strongly agreed that their organization collaborates with other organizations in their industry, 34.8% and another 34.8% agreed and strongly agreed respectively that there is efficient and effective change management system in the organization, 44.9% strongly agreed their organization has developed and maintained strategic partnerships, and 51.7% strongly agreed that their organization continuously reviews business strategies on operations of the market and its products. Finally, 58.4% of the respondents strongly agreed that leadership is visibly involved in all coordination activities in the organization. The table below shows that the majority of respondents strongly Agreed with all statements of Coordination.

Standard deviations range between 0.66 and 0.97, indicating a moderate spread around the means. The variances follow a similar pattern, with values between 0.43 and 0.94.

The smallest variability is for the collaboration statement, which shows consensus among respondents, while the greatest variability is for the change management system.

All variables have negative skewness, meaning the data distribution is slightly left-tailed, with more responses clustered around higher agreement levels (agree/strongly agree).

The negatively skewed variable is leadership involvement (-1.47), suggesting a strong tendency toward agreement.

Descriptive Statistics Leadership

Table 1.1: Descriptive Statistics Results for Leadership Capability

N Statistic	Mini m	Max m	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviat ion	Skewness Statistic	Std. Error	Kurtosis Statistic	Std. Error	
Our hotel embraces setting goals and targets during operation	89	1	5	4.56	.67	-2.17	.26	7.76	.51
There is tolerance to questioning decision-making.	89	1	5	4.16	.90	-.98	.26	.74	.51
The management of the hotel believes in continuous planning.	89	1	5	4.46	.72	-1.70	.26	4.71	.51
My hotel has clear communication policies	85	1	5	4.34	.85	-1.43	.26	2.27	.52
In your opinion, are co/-workers supportive of one another regarding helping the hotel beat competition?	89	1	5	4.29	.83	-.1.21	.26	1.79	.51
The decision-making process in this hotel is effective	89	1	5	4.13	.92	-.99	.26	.70	.51
Our hotel is strong in learning from experience leading to experiencing good performance	67	2	5	4.46	.75	-1.23	.29	.79	.58
Valid N (listwise)	89								

1.4.2 Leadership Deployment: Descriptive Statistics

For this item, Likert scale questions were also administered. 62.9% strongly agreed that their organization embraces setting goals and targets in their operations, 42.7% strongly agreed there is tolerance to questioning on decision making, 56.2% strongly agreed that their management believes in continuous planning, 50.6% strongly agreed that their organization upholds clear communication policies, 48.3% strongly agreed that co-workers were supportive to one another when it came to helping the organization beat competition, 41.6% strongly agreed that the decision making process in their hotel is effective, and 44.9% strongly agreed that their organization is strong in learning from experience leading to realizing good performance.

Most Likert-type scale responses indicate strong agreement overall. Standard deviations vary from 0.67 to 0.92, suggesting moderate consistency in responses, whereas variances are relatively low, indicating minimal dispersion around the means. Skewness values are negative across all statements, showing a tendency toward higher agreement, and kurtosis values suggest some peakedness in the distributions, particularly for statements like "Our organization embraces setting goals and targets in operations" (kurtosis = 7.76). The responses were reliable, as evidenced by the relatively low standard errors of the mean (0.07 to 0.10), indicating precise estimates of the population mean.

1.4.3. Hotel Performance Measurement Descriptive Statistics

To measure Hotel Performance, 8 Likert scale questions were administered. 56.1% of valid respondents strongly agreed that their organization observes on time delivery to its customers, 45.5% strongly agreed that their organization has achieved the image of a trusted supplier, 60.6% strongly agreed that there are new products and services based on customer’s needs, and 56.7% of valid respondents strongly agreed that there were new processes to improve efficiency in their organization, 64.2% strongly agreed that the organization had gained new customers recently, 59.7% strongly agreed there was high customer retention, 52.2% strongly agreed that customer needs are responded to swiftly, and 56.1% strongly agreed that the company’s customer groups and market segments are clearly defined and selected.

The mean scores ranged from 4.33 to 4.57, indicating that respondents generally agreed or strongly agreed with the statements. The standard errors of the mean (S.E. Mean) are consistently low (0.07–0.10), suggesting reliable estimates of the population means. Standard deviations range from 0.56 to 0.78, indicating moderate variability in responses, whereas variances range from 0.31 to 0.61.

The skewness values are all negative, ranging from 0.54 to 1.35, which indicates a left-skewed distribution, meaning most respondents rated positively. Kurtosis values ranged from 0.75 to 1.45, suggesting that although some distributions were slightly flatter or peaked more than normal, responses remained largely consistent.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Std. Error	Kurtosis	Std. Error
The hotel observes delivery on-time and on specifications to its customers.	66	2	5	4.42	.75	-1.11	.29	.58	.58
The hotel has achieved the image of a trusted supplier and is tolerant to questioning	66	3	5	4.33	.08	-.54	.29	.75	.58

decision-making.

New products and services are being developed according to customer needs.	66	2	5	4.50	.71	-1.35	.29	1.451	.58
There are processes to improve efficiency.	67	2	5	4.42	.78	-1.29	.29	1.20	.58
The hotel has gained new customers recently	67	3	5	4.55	.66	-1.19	.29	.25	.58
The hotel has high customer retention.	67	3	5	4.57	.56	-.82	.29	.37	.58
Customers' needs are responded to promptly	67	3	5	4.43	.66	-.74	.29	-.48	.58
The company's customer groups and market segments are clearly defined and selected	66	2	5	4.42	.75	-1.11	.29	.58	.58
Valid N (list wise)	89								

Table 1.2 Descriptive statistics of hotels performance

Factor Analysis Results

Factor analysis was performed for the three variables of the study. The factor analysis results for each variable are presented below. These variables include coordination, leadership, and organizational performance.

1.4.4 Coordination Capability deployment

The results indicate that one factor underlies the deployment of coordination capability. The factor was extracted as having an eigenvalue of 1.0 or higher. The extracted factors explain 43.7% of the variance in coordination as shown in table 1.1. The first factor explains 69.5%, while the second factor explains 17.1%.

Table 1. 3: Total Variance Explained for Coordination Capability Deployment Factors

	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.29	69.5%	69.5%	3.06	43.7%	43.7%	3.06	43.7%	43.7%
2	.42	9.0%	78.5%						
3	.28	6.0%	84.5%						
4	.28	5.9%	90.4%						
5	.20	4.2%	94.6%						
6	.15	3.2%	97.8%						
7	.10	2.2%	100.0%						

Table 1.3 coordination capability deployment

Seven items loaded high on first factor. They included statements that our organization is strong in operational coordination (.55), the organization collaborates with other organizations (.39), there is efficient and effective change management system in the organization (.85), the organization has developed and maintained strategic partnerships (.59), the organization continuously reviews business strategies on operations of the market and its products (.65), there is effective coordination within the various organizational activities, resources and services available in this organization (.79), and leadership is visibly involved in all coordination activities in the organization (.70).

Table 1. 4: Rotated Component Matrix for Coordination Capability Deployment Factors

	Component	
	1	2
Our hotel organization is strong in operational coordination.	.55	
Our hotel organization also collaborates with other organizations in the industry.	0.39	
An efficient and effective change management system in a hotel organization	0.85	
The hotel organization has developed and maintained strategic partnerships	0.85	
The hotel organization continuously review business strategies related to market operations and its products.	0.59	
The hotel organization continuously review business strategies related to market operations and its products.	0.65	
Effective coordination among the various hotel organizational activities, resources, and services available in the organization	0.79	
Leadership is involved in all coordination activities in the hotel organization.	0.70	

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.^a
 a. The rotation converged in 3 iterations.

Table 1.4 Rotated component matrix

The KMO statistic varies between 0 and 1. A value of 0 indicates that the sum of partial correlations is large relative to the sum of correlations, indicating diffusion in the pattern of correlations (hence, factor analysis is likely to be inappropriate). A value close to 1 indicates that correlation patterns are relatively compact; thus, factor analysis should yield distinct and reliable factors. Kaiser (1974) recommends accepting values greater than 0.5 as acceptable (values below this should lead the researcher to either collect more data or rethink which variables to include). Furthermore, values between 0.5 and 0.7 are average, values between 0.7 and 0.8 are good, values between 0.8 and 0.9 are great, and values above 0.9 are excellent. For these data, the value is 0.673, which falls into the range of being average: so, the factor analysis is appropriate for these data.

Bartlett’s measure tests the null hypothesis that the original correlation matrix is an identity matrix. For factor analysis to work, we need relationships between variables, and if the R-matrix were an identity matrix, then all correlation coefficients would be zero. Therefore, we want this test to be significant (i.e. have a significance value less than 0.05). A significant test tells us that the Rmatrix is not an identity matrix; therefore, there are some relationships between the variables we hope to include in the analysis. For these data, Bartlett’s test is highly significant (p< 0.00, and therefore factor analysis is appropriate).

KMO and Bartlett’s test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.87
Approx. Chi-Square	
Bartlett’s test of sphericity	18.603
df	
Sig.	.00

1.4.5 Factor analysis of leadership deployment

The factor analysis reveals a single-factor structure explaining 27% of the total variance in organizational practices and culture. The initial eigenvalue of 2.14 for the first factor, along with low initial communalities (.11 to .48), suggests moderate shared variance among items. In the rotated factor matrix, all items load onto this single factor with moderate loadings ranging from .34 to .63, with decision-making effectiveness (.63) and communication policies (.62) showing the strongest factor loadings. This unidimensional structure suggests that these organizational elements—including goal-setting, decision-making, planning, communication, teamwork, and learning represent interconnected aspects of leadership deployment.

Table 1.5: Factor analysis of leadership deployment

Total Variance Explained

	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.14	59.5%	59.5%	1.89	27.0%	27.0%	1.89	27.0%	27.0%
2	.48	13.4%	72.9%						
3	.29	8.1%	81.1%						
4	.24	6.6%	87.7%						
5	.18	5.0%	92.7%						
6	.15	4.1%	96.9%						
7	.11	3.1%	100.0%						

Seven items loaded high on first factor. They included statements that the organization embraces setting goals and targets in operation (.49), there is tolerance to questioning on decision making (.34), the management of the organization believes in continuous planning (.36), my organization upholds clear communication policies (.62), in your opinion, are co-workers supportive to one another when it comes to helping the organization beat competition (.51), the decision making process in this organization is effective (.63), and our organization is strong in learning from experience leading to realizing goals (.59).

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy for the leadership model yielded an overall value of 0.91, indicating an excellent level of factorability. Bartlett’s test of sphericity returned a significant result with a p-value of 0.02902, indicating that the correlation matrix significantly differs from the identity matrix. These results suggest that the variables are sufficiently correlated to conduct factor analysis.

Table 1.6: Rotated Component Matrix for Leadership Capability Deployment Factors

	Component	
	1	2
Our organization embraces setting goals and targets in operations.	0.34	
There is tolerance to questioning in decision-making.	0.49	
The management of the hotel believes in continuous planning.	0.36	
The hotel upholds clear communication policies.	0.62	
In your opinion, are co- workers supportive of one another when it comes to helping the organization beat competition?	0.51	
Decision making in this organization is effectiveness	0.63	
The hotel is strong in learning from experience, leading to good performance.	0.59	

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.^a
 a. The rotation converged in 3 iterations.

The KMO statistic varies between 0 and 1. A value of 0 indicates that the sum of partial correlations is large relative to the sum of correlations, indicating diffusion in the pattern of correlations (hence, factor analysis is likely to be inappropriate). A value close to 1 indicates that correlation patterns are relatively compact; thus, factor analysis should yield distinct and reliable factors. Kaiser (1974) recommends accepting values greater than 0.5 as acceptable (values below this should lead the researcher to either collect more data or rethink which variables to include). Furthermore, values between 0.5 and 0.7 are average, values between 0.7 and 0.8 are good, values between 0.8 and 0.9 are great, and values above 0.9 are excellent. For these data, the value is 0.673, which falls into the range of being average: so, the factor analysis is appropriate for these data.

Bartlett’s measure tests the null hypothesis that the original correlation matrix is an identity matrix. For factor analysis to work, we need relationships between variables, and if the R-matrix were an identity matrix, then all correlation coefficients would be zero. Therefore, we want this test to be significant (i.e. have a significance value less than 0.05). A significant test tells us that the Rmatrix is not an identity matrix; therefore, there are some relationships between the variables we hope to include in the analysis. For these data, Bartlett’s test is highly significant ($p < 0.00$, and therefore factor analysis is appropriate).

KMO and Bartlett’s test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.91
Approx. Chi-Square	
Bartlett’s test of sphericity	14.056
df	
Sig.	.02

1.4.6 Factor Analysis on Hotel Performance

The total variance explained shows that one factor accounts for 61.1% of the variance, with an eigenvalue of 2.34, indicating that it is the primary driver of the construct. The rotated factor matrix reveals that all items load

significantly onto the single factor, with loadings ranging from 0.39 to 0.62. The item “The company's customer groups and market segments are clearly defined and selected” has the highest loading (0.62), indicating it is most strongly associated with the factor. Overall, the items align well with the same underlying construct.

Table 1.7: Total Variance Explained for Organizational Performance Factors

Component	Initial Eigenvalues Squared			Extraction Rotation			Sums of Sums of		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulativ e %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.340	61.1	61.1	2.13	26.6	26.6	2.13	26.6	26.6
2	.034	8.9	69.9						
3	.28	7.4	77.3						
4	.25	6.6	83.9						
5	.23	6.0	89.9						
6	.16	4.1	94.0						
7	.14	3.6	97.6						
8	.09	2.4	100.0						

Seven items loaded high on first factor. They included statements that the organization observes delivery on time and on specifications to its customers (.56), the organization has achieved the image of a trusted supplier (.46), there are new products and services based on customer needs (.49), there are processes to improve efficiency (.60), the organization has gained new customers recently (.43), the organization has a high customer retention (.39) customers’ needs are responded swiftly (0.53), and the company’s customer groups and market segments are clearly defined and selected (.62).

Table 1.8: Rotated Component Matrix of Hotel Performance Factors

The organization observes delivery on-time and on specification to its customers	0.56
The organization has achieved the image of a trusted supplier as shown in	0.46
There are new products and services based on customer needs	0.49
There are processes to improve efficiency	0.60
The organization has recently gained new customers recently	0.43

The organization has high customer retention.

0.39

Customer needs are responded to immediately at

0.53

The company's customer groups and market segments are clearly defined and selected . 0.62

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.^a

a. The rotation converged in 6 iterations.

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy is 0.495, which is close to 0.5 hence average and shows that patterns of correlations are relatively compact and that factor analysis should yield distinct and reliable factors. Factor analysis was therefore appropriate for these data. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is highly significant ($p < 0.000$), so factor analysis is appropriate.

KMO and Bartlett's test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.495
Approx. Chi-Square	9.7413
Bartlett's test of sphericity	
df	7
Sig.	0.2037

1.4.7 Key effects of conceptual model on hypotheses

To determine the effect of coordination and leadership capability deployment on performance, the relevant null hypotheses was postulated as follows:

H₁: Strategic competitive response capability does not influence the organizational performance Corporate hotels in Kenya.

1.4.8 Correlation Analysis

A correlation analysis was performed to establish the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The results in table 1.9 show that coordination capability deployment was positively correlated with organizational performance at the 99% confidence level ($r = .777, p = 0.001$). The results imply a direct relationship

between coordination capability deployment and organizational performance, which means that the higher the level of coordination, the higher the organizational performance.

The results show that leadership capability deployment is positively correlated with organizational performance at the 99% confidence level ($r=.801$, $p=0.001$). These findings show a direct relationship between leadership capability deployment and corporate hotel performance, where higher leadership capability levels indicate higher organizational performance.

Table 1. 9: Correlation Analysis

		Coordination	Leadershi p Deployme nt	Organization al Performanc e
Coordination capability deployment	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1.000 .000 89	.836 .000 89	.777 .000 89
Leadership capability deployment	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.836 .000	1.000 .000	.801 .000
Organizational Hotperforman ce	Pearson Corr. Sign(2 tails) N	.89 .777 .000 67	.89 .801 .000 67	.67 1.000 .000 67

** . The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

1.4.9 Hypothesis Testing

Regression analysis was conducted to test the linear relationship between the independent variable “corporate hotel performance” and the independent variables “coordination and leadership capability deployment.”

Simple linier regression analysis was performed to test the study hypothesis H_1-H_2 . The model used for the analysis is $Y=\beta_0+ \beta_1X_1+ \beta_2X_2+ \varepsilon$. The results presented in table 1.9 show that the predictor variables, coordination and leadership explain 45.7% of the change in the dependent variable, organizational performance ($R^2=.457$).

Table 5. 0: Model Summary

Model	R	Adjusted R Squared	Standard Error in Estimate
1	.83	.69	.30

a. Predictors: (Constant), Coordination, Leadership

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the fitness of the analysis model. The results of the F value show that the analysis model used was fit and that the results obtained were significant; hence, they did not occur by chance ($F=70.55$, $p=.000$). These results are shown in table 5.1.

Table 5. 1: ANOVA

Model		Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
	Regression	12.73	2	6.37	70.55	.000
1	Residual	5.77	64	0.09		
	Total	18.51	66			

a. Dependent Variable :Hotel Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Coordination, Leadership

Table 5. 2: Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized	Coefficients	Standardised	t	
			B	Std. Error	Sig
(Constant)	.86	.31	.00	2.77	.007
Coordination	.32	.10	.37	3.7	.003
Leadership	.49	.12	.50	4.14	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Hotel Performance

The model summary indicates that the regression model explains a substantial proportion of the variance in organizational performance. The coefficient of determination (R^2) is 0.69, implying that approximately 69% of the variability in organizational performance can be explained by the independent variables included in the model (table 4.19). The adjusted R^2 , which accounts for the number of predictors, is 0.68, suggesting a slight reduction because of the inclusion of multiple variables. The R-value of 0.83 indicates a strong positive correlation between the predicted and observed values of organizational performance. This suggests that the model fits the data reasonably well.

The ANOVA table for the regression analysis indicate that the overall model is highly significant. The regression sum of squares is 12.73, and the residual sum of squares is 5.77, leading to a total sum of squares of 18.51. The mean square for the regression is 6.37, and the F-statistic is 70.55, which is significantly higher than the critical

value. The p-value of 0.000 (less than 0.05) suggests that the independent variables in the model significantly predict organizational performance. Therefore, the regression model is statistically significant and provides a good fit for the data.

The coefficient table provides insights into the relationship between the independent variables (coordination and leadership deployment) and organizational performance. The unstandardized coefficient for coordination is 0.32, indicating that, for each unit increase in coordination, organizational performance is expected to increase by 0.32 units, holding other variables constant. Similarly, the unstandardized coefficient for leadership deployment is 0.49, suggesting that each unit increase in leadership deployment results in a 0.49-unit increase in organizational performance.

The standardized coefficients (Beta) indicate the relative strength of these predictors. Leadership deployment has a stronger influence on organizational performance (Beta = 0.50) than compared to coordination (Beta = 0.37), indicating that leadership deployment has a greater effect on organizational performance.

All predictors were statistically significant, with p-values well below 0.05: coordination ($p = 0.003$), leadership deployment ($p = 0.000$), and constant ($p = 0.007$). This indicates that both coordination and leadership deployment are significant predictors of organizational performance.

2. Discussion

The objective of this study was to determine the effect of deploying coordination and leadership capabilities deployment on the performance of corporate hotel facilities in Kenya. The hypothesis *H01 Coordination and leadership capability deployment has no significant relationship with corporate hotel facility performance*. The results show that coordination and leadership capability deployment has a positive statistically significant relationship with performance, thus rejecting the null hypothesis. The higher the level of coordination and leadership, the better the organizational performance. Internal operations and collaboration with external stakeholders are two important elements of coordination factor in coordination, while tolerance of questioning in decision making, target setting, and planning are important in leadership.

3. Conclusions and Implications

This study concludes that coordination capability is exhibited by the component, and the organization is strong in operational coordination. The study also concludes that coordination significantly influences the organizational performance of corporate hotel facilities in Kenya. Coordination has a positive relationship with performance. The higher the level of coordination, the better the performance of the hotel. These findings are in agreement with those by (Teece, 2011), Allred, (2011), (Frese, 2008) and (Helfat, 2007), who noted that coordination or integration capability is the firm's ability to assess the value of existing resources and integrate them to shape new competences. Through coordination, essentials from the external environment are imported into the organization, and these include staff and their placement as well as other relevant factors of production, such as directing and giving clear focus that help in actualizing performance. Coordination is also seen as part of planning; it tells what to include in a good plan and how to execute it, as part of organizing as it takes the first lead (Gulick & Urwirck, 1957).

The study also concludes that Leadership capability is exhibited by the component, that there is tolerance to questioning decision making, and that the organization embraces setting targets and in planning in operation. The study also concludes that leadership has a significant influence on hotel facilities in Kenya. Leadership has a positive relationship with performance. The higher the level of leadership, the better the performance of the hotel.

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